

Title: The Julia Wedgwood Site

Author: Alison Stone

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URL: <https://www.juliawedgwood.org>

Abstract: a website dedicated to the writings and thought of Julia Wedgwood, an intellectual icon of the Victorian era. Makes available a full set of Wedgwood's writings, including many anonymous essays now identified as hers for the first time. Also provides further resources and readings, details of the methods used to identify the essays, biographical information, and guides for further research and teaching.

The Julia Wedgwood Site

Welcome to a site dedicated to the writings and thought of Julia Wedgwood, an intellectual icon of the Victorian era.

Explore Wedgwood's Writings

Julia Wedgwood (1833-1913) was a major intellectual force of the Victorian period. She wrote two biographies, two major books - *The Moral Ideal* (1888) and *The Message of Israel* (1894) - and over 100 journal articles, a few collected as *Nineteenth-Century Teachers* (1909).

She was the niece of Charles Darwin, the second love of Robert Browning, and a mentor to E. M. Forster. Her female friends included Harriet Martineau, George Eliot, and Frances Power Cobbe.

Some of her key interests:

- How do we reconcile science and religion, Darwinism and Christianity?
- How have ideas developed historically by reacting against each other?
- What moral lessons can we learn from the major world civilisations?
- What's distinctive about Christian and modern thought compared to Ancient Greece and Rome?
- What is nature?
- Do we have free will? How should we understand our existence, torn between spirit and nature?
- How does fiction illuminate historical upheavals in thought?

Wedgwood was also a feminist and advocate for animal welfare.

You can navigate around the site using the Menu button (three lines on mobile) at the top right.